

Transition Metal Complexes of vic-Oxime-Ketone and Diamine

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Copper, nickel, cobalt and iron complexes of 2,3-dioxobutyranilide 2-oxime in presence of benzidine or p-phenylenediamine were prepared and their magnetic susceptibility was determined at room temperature. The formation and the nature of these complexes are discussed.

PFIEFFER¹, Masuda² and Talati and Patel³ studied the transition metal complexes of schiff bases of 2,3-dioxobutane monoxime and 2,3-dioxobutyranilide 2-oxime. Schiff bases of 2,3-dioxobutyranilide 2-oxime with aromatic and aliphatic monoamines and their transition metal complexes have been prepared^{3,4,5}. However, attempts to prepare the schiff bases of the above oxime-ketone with aromatic diamines were unsuccessful. Hence the schiff base-formation was carried out by treating the oxime-ketone with benzidine or p-phenylenediamine in presence of a transition metal salt. Transition metal complexes of copper, nickel, cobalt and iron were obtained from these reactions. On the basis of analysis, they are formulated as shown in (I), (II) and (III).

We find that the complexes formed by using the metal chloride or sulphate are different from those obtained by using the metal acetate in presence of a diamine. The ligand displaces acetic acid completely from the metal acetate but is coordinatively bonded to the metal chloride or sulphate. A metal-to-ligand ratio of 1 : 1 is observed in the case of addition complex and of 1 : 2 in the case of substitution complex. The isolation of the addition product leads us to suggest that the reaction mechanism for the formation of the products can be represented by the following set of equations, where HX represents acetic, hydrochloric or $\frac{1}{2}$ sulphuric acid and LH represents the ligand :

When a sparingly soluble product is obtained in reaction (i), the subsequent reactions would be almost unobserved.

All the complexes of type (I) contain the schiff base; however complexes of types (II) and (III) contain schiff base to a different extent. Hence it is suggested that the product of reaction (i) undergoes condensation reaction with the amine, before the elimination reaction (ii) takes place. And, the product of reaction (iii) may or may not undergo further condensation reaction with the amine, depending on the nature of the metal ion.

The copper complexes (II) exhibit low magnetic moment which may be attributed to the antiferromagnetic interactions. The cobalt complex (III) possesses magnetic moment which is characteristic of square planar or tetragonal complexes of cobalt. The magnetic moments of the nickel and iron complexes (I) indicate the existence of two unpaired electrons in these complexes.

(a) *Chloride method* : (for Cu and Ni) :

The solutions of copper chloride (or nickel chloride) 2,3-dioxobutanilide-2-oxime and benzidine (or *p*-phenylene diamine) in ethanol were mixed in the molar proportions of 1 : 2 : 1 respectively. The

common organic solvents except pyridine and dimethylformamide. (OBCu; OBCo; OPCu, OPCo).

(c) *Sulphate method* : (for Fe) :

The solutions of ferrous sulphate (in water), 2,3-dioxobutanilide 2-oxime (in alcohol) and benzidine (in alcohol) were mixed in the molar proportion of 1 : 2 : 1 respectively. Precipitates were gradually obtained which were left overnight. These were filtered, washed with very dilute alcohol and dried. The product is soluble in common organic solvents (OBF_e).

The colour, m.pt., analysis, etc. of these complexes are presented in Table 1.

Magnetic susceptibility :

Mass magnetic susceptibility (χ_g) of these compounds was determined on Gouy's magnetic balance at room temperature using mercury (II) tetrathiocyanate cobaltate (II) as the reference compound. The magnetic moments are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1. TRANSITION METAL COMPLEXES OF VIC-OXIME-KETONE AND DIAMINE

No.	Complex	Colour	M.P. (°C)	Formula	Analysis				Magnetic moment (B.M.)
					%M Found	%N Found	%M Reqd.	N% Reqd.	
1.	OB-CuCl	Brown	> 300	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ Cu	15.32	10.27	15.32	10.42	2.23
2.	OP-NiCl	Ash	> 300	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ Ni	14.08	12.41	13.79	13.15	3.30
3.	OB-Cu	Greenish brown	> 300	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₅ Cu	12.54	12.35	11.60	12.77	1.60
4.	OB-Co	Dull red	> 300	C ₃₂ H ₃₀ N ₆ Co	9.01	13.43	8.99	12.86	2.59
5.	OB-Fe	Blue	> 300	C ₃₂ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₁₀ SFe	7.60	11.83	7.46	11.23	3.36
6.	OP-Cu	Greenish brown	> 300	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₇ Cu	13.19	12.69	12.42	13.68	1.59
7.	OP-Co	Violet	> 300	C ₂₉ H ₃₆ N ₇ O ₉ Co	8.71	14.09	8.60	14.32	2.13

mixture became turbid, gradually forming precipitates. These were refluxed on water bath for about two hours and left overnight. They were filtered, washed with water, alcohol and ether and dried. They are insoluble in water and all common organic solvents except pyridine and dimethylformamide. (OBCuCl, OPNiCl).

(b) *Acetate method* : (for Cu and Co) :

The solutions of metal acetate, 2,3-dioxobutanilide-2-oxime and benzidine (or *p*-phenylene diamine) in ethanol were mixed in the molar proportions of 1 : 2 : 1 respectively. The mixture became turbid, gradually forming precipitates. These were refluxed on water bath for about 2 hr and left overnight. They were filtered, washed with water, alcohol and ether and dried. They are insoluble in water and all

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References

1. P. PFEIFFER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1930, **63**, 1811.
2. I. MASUDA, *J. Chem. Soc. (Japan)*, 1961, **82**, 1350.
3. A. M. TALATI and T. I. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 205; *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, **6**, 667.
4. A. M. TALATI and K. B. SHAH (unpublished data).
5. M. R. PATEL and B. N. MANKAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **41**, 841.